

SUMEX DELIVERABLE D5.2

SKETCH NOTES: SUMMARY REPORT OF THE PEER-LEARNING WORKSHOPS

Summary:

This document summarises the key findings from the peer-learning workshops organised in the SUMEX project between November 2021 and November 2022.

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1 INTRODUCTION

To foster sustainable mineral production in the European Union, SUMEX ([Sustainable Management in Extractive industries](#)) has established a Sustainability Framework for the extractive industries in Europe. It did so by taking into account the Sustainable Development Goals, the European Green Deal, as well as EU Social License to Operate considerations and involves stakeholders from industry, government, academia and civil society from all across the EU. This SUMEX Framework offers a roadmap for the European extractive industry through its mapping of current and future priorities that will allow the sector to transform towards sustainability. As well, the Framework includes evaluative criteria that stakeholders can use to assess the sustainability of projects, extractive operations or mineral raw-material products.

In addition to the development of this Framework, the SUMEX project organised **four peer-learning workshops and a summary workshop** to address and discuss SUMEX themes that are categorised as illustrated on the faces of the SUMEX project cube at right (Figure 1-1): the five SUMEX focus areas (front face), the extractives value chain (right side), and four specific sustainability related policy aspects (top face). The **SUMEX focus areas** consider socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, land-use planning, health & safety, data reporting, and permitting. These focus areas can be considered within the stages of extraction, which are divided here (right side) into pre-exploration/ exploration, operation, and closure/ post-closure. SUMEX concentrates its efforts on the four sustainability related policy issues social, environmental, economic, and mineral.

Figure 1-1: SUMEX cube

Contributing to the SUMEX challenge for a more uniform understanding of sustainable management in the extractive industries, the five SUMEX project workshops brought together peers in the extractives industries, extractives authorities and civil society on the three levels – EU, Member State and regional – to start and create a Community of Practice (CoP) focused on applying sustainability principles. Ahead of the workshops, a concise and coherent digital survey was conducted in October 2021 to better understand these stakeholders’ needs for incorporating sustainability practices and to understand how stakeholders best learn. The [survey results](#) were considered to reflect stakeholders’ diverse capacity-building needs as they intersect with the five SUMEX focus areas. The results contributed to designing learning materials and to organising the agendas for the four regional, peer-learning workshops and the summary workshop.

The stakeholder needs identified in the survey were also considered when establishing the 3L (Learners and Leaders League) and a broader CoP. In addition to the physical exchange format with regional peer learning workshops the SUMEX project developed digital capacity-building materials in a [Massive Open Online Course \(MOOC\)](#) and a [digital knowledge repository](#) (both subsumed as the [SUMEX Toolkit](#)). These tools were further supported by the discussions during the four regional workshops, the majority of which were organised as in-person events. The results of the discussions from the four regional events were brought together at the final summary workshop held as part of the Raw Materials Week 2022 in Brussels on 17 November 2022.

Overall, it was seen that in-person dialogue between stakeholders representing different perspectives – civil society, industry and governments – is important to promoting more sustainability concepts in extractives activities and to understand the different stakeholders’ views.

2 PEER-LEARNING WORKSHOP STRUCTURE AND SCHEDULE

Each of the four macro regions – separated by EU region into north, east, south, and west– hosted one workshop (see Figure 2-1). The workshops aimed at **physically bringing together practitioners in the extractives industries to enable networking** and to **exchange experience and good-practice examples** through presentations and discussions that addressed extractives activities as they intersect with sustainability principles.

Figure 2-1: EU macro-regions per peer-learning workshop and topics

Titled “Regional workshops: How can sustainable extraction in Europe be supported? Connect with other practitioners!”, each workshop addressed **two of the five SUMEX focus areas**: socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, land-use planning, health & safety, data reporting, and permitting (see Figure 1-1 above). The topic **permitting** as most relevant basis was on the agenda of all four regional workshops. The four remaining topics were each assigned to one regional workshop (see Table 1). **Good-practice cases** were presented during each of the workshops. These presentations set the stage for **smaller working group sessions** that allowed workshop participants to exchange their ideas and share their experience. These discussions were supported by **expert (panel) discussions** with panellists representing different perspectives: NGO/ CSO, industry, permitting authorities, and/or policy from different levels.

The peer-learning workshops sought to bring people together physically. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the first regional workshop West in November 2021 had to occur digitally over four hours of presentations and breakout discussion groups. All other workshops were held in person. The first day of the three in-person regional workshops involved approximately eight hours of presentations and discussions. On the second day, participants were invited to join a site visit to a local mineral extraction location.

Detailed information on the five peer-learning workshops is provided in the Annexes (see Chapter 5).

Table 1: SUMEX Focus areas per (regional) workshop

Regional workshop		West	North	East	South	Summary WS
		23 Nov 2021	20 Apr 2022	31 May 2022	22 Jun 2022	17 Nov 2022
Topic		Digital (TEAMS)	Helsinki, Finland	Tallinn, Estonia	Seville, Spain	Brussels, Belgium
SUMEX Focus area	Socio-economic and environmental impact assessments		X			X
	Land-use planning	X				X
	Health & safety			X		X
	Reporting				X	X
	Permitting	X	X	X	X	X

3 KEY FINDINGS FROM THE WORKSHOPS

The results from the SUMEX workshops overall confirmed the **need to continue discussions between different stakeholders to support more sustainable management in the extractives industries**. Dialogue is the foundation for exchanging information and understanding different views. Despite the restrictions from the COVID-19 pandemic, stakeholders were eager to learn from each other by exchanging ideas and sharing their experience of sustainability approaches in working practices of the extractives industries.

In the following box the overall key findings are summarised.

- Dialogue between all stakeholder groups is essential
- Social license to operate is important and an ongoing process
- Institutionalisation of rules for SLO is crucial
- Common definition of ‘sustainability’ is needed
- Extractive sector needs to shift to circular-economy business models
- SUMEX Framework is appropriate at the moment but will need adaption with changes in the future

In all workshops and across all SUMEX focus areas, the issue of **social license to operate (SLO)** and social engagement were intensively discussed. SLO is not a documented certificate but is instead a process throughout the entire lifetime of an extraction site, from planning to post-closure. This continuous process needs to be maintained and constantly developed. The Social Impact Assessment¹ (SIA) is an institutionalisation of an SLO

¹ Definition of Social impact assessment: SIA includes the processes of analysing, monitoring and managing the intended and unintended social consequences, both positive and negative, of planned interventions (policies, programs, plans, projects) and any social change processes invoked by those interventions. International Association for Impact Assessment (<https://www.iaia.org/pdf/special-publications/SP2.pdf>)

management process. (For further information on socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, please see chapter 3.3).

Continuous dialogue between all stakeholder groups is essential to and builds the basis for obtaining SLO. Communication through proactive local engagement, including public consultations, should start early in planning a new project and last beyond the end of the project (post-closure time). The shared information needs to be transparent, clear, easy to understand in language and length (using e.g. info-graphics or virtual site presentations) to build trust in local communities and ensure open dialogue between all stakeholder groups. Furthermore, dialogues with civil society need to occur in several different forms other than only public meetings. This could include holding (in-person and digital) workshops and public surveys and publishing action plans or other data in a proactive and transparent way. Especially in areas where mineral extraction is a new activity for local communities, dialogue is even more relevant. Through such dialogues, the benefits and risks of the extractive activities for the local communities should be made transparent.

In this context it was also discussed how awareness in the broader population needs to be raised about raw materials and the need for their extraction to maintain our current society. For example, the positive as well as challenging aspects of extraction projects could be included in learning materials in school curricula to reach out to the broader population.

Directly impacting the effectiveness of discussions in several workshops and at the final summary workshop, the **definition of 'sustainability'** and hence 'sustainable management' was raised. Despite the fact that the term has a three-decade long history in international governance (since the United Nations Conferences on Environment and Development and its Declarations) and is used across multiple sectors and in multiple international organisations' operating principles and commitments (not the least the EU Principles for sustainable raw materials and the SUMEX Sustainability Framework), the term still eludes the conceptual and operational meaning for many extractive sector actors: what does each person mean when speaking of 'sustainability'? what does the extractives industry mean with the term? Meaningful dialogue can only occur once a common definition of 'sustainability' is documented, disseminated and enters into use. During the final summary workshop held in Brussels, Belgium, on 17 November 2022, participants were asked in a digital poll what they understood 'sustainability' to mean. The main responses, visible in Figure 3-1 below, included themes related to a holistic perspective: the environment, human rights, economics, and sufficiency for a long-term future.

Figure 3-2: ‘In your point of view, which of the following has the biggest influence on making the transition to sustainable extractive industries happen?’ at summary workshop in Brussels, Belgium on 17 November 2022; Participant poll results (n=48)

The discussions in the summary workshop also highlighted that the **current specifications of the SUMEX Sustainability Framework are appropriate** (see Figure 3-3). These Framework criteria, however, might change as technology and innovations progress and our understanding about the social, environmental, political and economic needs increases. This is reflected in the answer “does not go far enough”.

Figure 3-3: ‘The SUMEX Framework...’ describing the extent of the SUMEX Framework, at summary workshop in Brussels, Belgium on 17 November 2022; Participant poll results (n=49)

The following subsections summarise the discussions from the regional workshops based on the five SUMEX focus areas.

3.1 PERMITTING

The SUMEX focus area ‘Permitting’ was addressed and discussed in all four regional workshops and the summary workshop. Generally, three main points were seen in the presentations and discussions:

- Having strict rules for extractives activities can function as a driver for change towards more sustainability;
- Rules, Regulations and Directives impacting permitting for extractive activities, including the EU-wide consistent transposition of the [Birds Directive](#) and the [Habitats Directive](#) (e.g. open and transparent assessment of extractive activities, a clear ex-ante definition of “site integrity” in combination with a clear translation of site-level conservation objectives in Natura 2000 areas); and
- Clear communication between industry and public authorities – i.e. transparency of goals, risks and advantages in extractive projects and at site operations – leads to trust between all stakeholders to develop successful projects.

In the following box the key aspects of the discussions on permitting are summarised.

- **A regulatory framework as driver for change**
- **Clear interpretation, concrete objectives (e.g. nature conservation), and consistent implementation of rules is necessary**
- **Communication is critical to success of new and existing projects**

Rules

In the discussions addressing existing rules, it became clear that **a regulatory framework, such as the Water Framework Directive, mandate companies to change and demand implementation of identified good practices.** However, participants often indicated that extractive operations need to still be economically viable (i.e. competitive with producers outside the EU) for the EU to not risk losing all operations in its territories. Furthermore, consistent implementation of EU Directives is needed without the possibility for different interpretations when being enforced. EU rules, Regulations and Directives must be consistently implemented to ensure an equal standard across national jurisdictions.

Extraction in protected areas & communication

Gaining permitting rights for extraction in protected areas, such as **Natura 2000** areas, was discussed intensively during several workshops. As an initial step, it is pertinent to identify and in detail understand the conservation status and impact of the extractive activity on the protected area so that the conservation objectives can be addressed by the extraction company.

Figure 3-4: Maria Nyberg presents ‘Sustainability approaches in Europe’ at summary workshop in Brussels, Belgium on 17 November 2022

In all new projects – but especially in protected areas – the **engagement and trust of local communities is key.** The basis for a social license to operate (see more details on SLO in the introduction to chapter 3) is continuous communication with all stakeholder groups. Not only the engagement of all stakeholders should be in place from the beginning. Also, the approach ‘think about the end from the beginning’ should be kept in mind. This

implies that compensation measures should be considered from the beginning of a project and should include aspects for recovering degraded areas, even ones that are not damaged directly by industry. It is highly recommendable for extractive companies to work closely with administrations and local stakeholders before applying for a permit to ensure that all aspects are covered with the confidence of the authorities and the surrounding communities.

Role of permitting authorities

The role of the permitting authorities was seen in various forms. While the decisions of permitting authorities are bound by legislation, such authorities can also focus on specific sustainability aspects in permitting processes.

Presentations on Permitting

The following presentations (available on the [SUMEX website](#) and summarised in Annexes 1-5 below), specifically addressed practice cases and issues related to permitting in the EU:

- “Implementation of the Nature directives in EU member states: Guidance for inspection in nature protected areas” by Dr. Gisela Holzgraefe (Ministry for Energy Transition, Agriculture, Environment, Nature and Digitalization of the State of Schleswig-Holstein, Germany) and by Lia Mergulhão (ICNF – Instituto da Conservação da Natureza e das Florestas, I.P., Portugal); [West workshop](#) (23 November 2021)
- “Industry’s approach to the Water Framework Directive” by Ylva Ågren (Boliden); [North workshop](#) (20 April 2022)
- “The unique hybrid business model of combining power storage services and deep granite mining and its environmental footprint” by Peep Siitam (Energiasalv); [East workshop](#) (31 May 2022)
- “Sustainable mining in Natura 2000 zone” by Ivan Ivanov and Gergana Todorova (Dundee Precious Metals); [East workshop](#) (31 May 2022)
- “ASSIMAGRA: Permitting procedures and experience in Natura 2000 areas in Portugal” by Nelson Cristo (ASSIMAGRA); [South workshop](#) (22 June 2022)
- “Closing the loop in quarry extraction” by Kjartan Eggebø (VELDE); [Summary workshop](#) (17 November 2022)

3.2 LAND-USE PLANNING

The SUMEX focus area ‘Land-use planning’ was a central topic in the regional workshop west. Two main aspects were identified:

- Early stakeholder engagement is critical. This means local communities, in particular indigenous communities, need to be involved from the first project conceptualisations.
- At the beginning of laying new project plans, closure, remediation and aftercare management plans need to be considered.

In the following box the key aspects of the discussions on land-use planning are summarised.

- **Early stakeholder engagement is critical**
- **Closure, remediation and aftercare management plans need to be considered at project start**

As described under Chapter 3, SLO and stakeholder engagement was discussed intensively in all workshops - also under the land-use planning focus area. **Early stakeholder engagement** – in particular in indigenous communities – was highlighted in the land-use planning discussions.

A significant aspect involves considering from the beginning the final nature of an extraction project and hence the **closure, remediation and aftercare management plans**. These dynamic documents can strongly influence land-use planning decisions. The practice case of the Sauerland area (see presentation [“Practice case: Mining and Postmining in Germany – Examples from the Sauerland Area” by Michael Neuman](#)) was successful when post-mining plans (i.e. Final operating plan and Special operating plan) were developed and followed. While extractives activities are required in the EU to meet societal needs, they must occur with environmental and social protections.

Figure 3-5: Land-use planning discussion group 3 results; regional workshop west

Figure 3-6: Land-use planning discussion group 5 results; regional workshop west

Presentations on Land-use planning

The following presentations (available on the [SUMEX website](#) and summarised in Annexes 1-5 below), specifically addressed practice cases and issues related to Land-use planning in the EU:

- “Practice Case: Mineral Development in Ireland, a review of planning consent” by Sybil Berne MacCabe Durney Barnes, Ireland); [West workshop](#) (23 November 2021)
- “Mining and Post-mining in Germany – Examples from the Sauerland Area” by Michael Neumann independent consultant, Natural Resources Consulting, Germany); [West workshop](#) (23 November 2021)

3.3 SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENTS

During the second SUMEX workshop in Helsinki (FI), the SUMEX Focus area socio-economic impact assessments (SEIA) and environmental impact assessments (EIA) were discussed and several practice cases were presented. Overall, it was seen that completed EIAs and SEIAs are important for achieving a social license to operate (SLO). See detailed explanations on SLO aspects and community engagement in the introduction to chapter 3 above.

In the following box the key aspects of the discussions on socio-economic and environmental impact assessments are summarised.

- Social license to operate is important and an ongoing process
- Social impact Assessment is time-consuming
- Institutionalisation of rules for SLO is crucial

During workshop discussions, it became clear that the management process needs to include SEIA for a project to understand and track how a planned action will impact the life of communities. SEIA supports management in developing mitigation and compensation measures and in monitoring impacts of the intended project on the surrounding community. For the community, SEIA helps to benefit from or to adapt to changes that the development may bring.

It was broadly seen that, although **completing a socio-economic impact assessment may be a long process, it is worthwhile** for understanding the needs of the communities directly impacted by extraction.

Figure 3-7: Content slide of presentation by Rauno Sairinen presented during the regional workshop North

Many participants expressed a wish for **institutionalising SEIA**, much like EIA is a required process. If SEIA were a required step for permitting, authorities would prescribe a clear process and method for understanding the socio-economic impact. However, participants raised the concern of how to monitor such impacts as societal demands and values are fluid and might change.

Maintaining trust in a community is critical to ensuring SLO (see further explanation above in chapter 3), which requires **industry to be adaptive to socio-economic changes** throughout the lifetime of a project and beyond. **Continuous dialogue** with communities, and also between all extractives companies in a region, can support an exchange on different views and experiences and support a long-lasting social license to operate.

Presentations on socio-economic and environmental impact assessments

The following presentations (available on the [SUMEX website](#) and summarised in Annexes 1-5 below), specifically addressed practice cases and issues related to socio-economic and environmental impact assessment in the EU:

- “Social impact assessment and management meets SLO in mining” by Rauni Sairinen, University of Eastern Finland); [North workshop](#) (20 April 2022)
- “Interaction of communities engagement and sustainability” by Ulla Syriälä, Anglo American; [North workshop](#) (20 April 2022)
- “The unique hybrid business model of combining power storage services and deep granite mining and its environmental footprint” by Peep Siitam, Energiesalv Pakri OÜ; [East workshop](#) (31 May 2022)

3.4 HEALTH AND SAFETY

The SUMEX focus area ‘Health and safety’ (H&S) was a main topic during the regional workshop in Tallinn (EE) and during the summary workshop in Brussels (BE).

In the following box the key aspects of the discussions on health and safety are summarised.

- **Need for a ‘culture of safety’**
- **Existing H&S standards must be implemented**

Generally, it was seen that **H&S standards and rules are in place**. However, many countries have myriad different H&S standards that must be applied, making it challenging to ensure compliance. Harmonisation of the rules would make compliance easier to track and also easier for workers to learn.

Technological advances can significantly reduce risks to humans from extraction, especially in deep underground mines, where some of the greatest hazards can be found. Participants commented that more innovations should be supported and promoted. While technology innovations continue to reduce H&S risks, the **implementation of existing H&S regulations** is the basis to preventing injury or death. Employees need to actually follow the safety procedures already in place. For this, participants described how **more and more frequent training sessions** should be mandatory for workers to ensure the implementation. Broadly speaking, extractive companies need to invest in developing a **‘culture of safety’**. This should be set with good examples at the management level.

Participants commented that implementing H&S standards in mining companies is beneficial for both for the employees and for the company itself. Implementation of H&S standards protects corporate assets (i.e. the employees) and can promote a positive image of mining. Implementation of H&S standards and transparent and comparable reporting also directly impacts successfully achieving a **social license to operate (SLO)**.

PREVENTIVE ACTIONS - ZERO HARM POLICY

KGHM CUPRUM Research & Development Centre

Figure 3-8: Preventive actions at KGHM CUPRUM; slide presented by Krzysztof Fuławka during the regional workshop East and the summary workshop in Brussels

Presentation on Health and safety

The following presentation (available on the [SUMEX website](#) and summarised in Annexes 1-5 below), specifically addressed a practice case to H&S issues in the EU:

- “Health and safety challenges facing deep underground mines operators – case study from polish copper mines” by Krzysztof Fulawka, KGHM CUPRUM; [East workshop](#) (31 May 2022)

3.5 REPORTING

Reporting was mainly discussed at the regional workshop in Seville, Spain. The overall question addressed how reporting can support and improve sustainability in the extractive sector. Generally, it was seen that the EU is making efforts to address some of the issues, which were highlighted in the discussions:

- The non-financial reporting directive should be considered, including the extractive sector;
- Environmental data reporting is important to building trust, but this is yet not required; and
- Extractive industries seem to be reluctant to fully disclose information relevant to sustainability issues because some information may be commercially sensitive and/or there is potential for misinterpretation of the published data.

In the following box the key aspects of the discussions on reporting are summarised.

- Consider non-financial reporting directive
- Environmental data reporting is important to build trust, yet not required
- Industry is reluctant in full transparency (commercial information)

In the discussion, some historical context for mineral reporting was described. The framework for today’s reporting came out of the fraudulent practices in the 1970s and ’80s and focuses on data-quality control under three pillars: transparency, materiality and competence. While this framework serves financial stakeholders, it does not address sustainability aspects. More uniform **reporting of non-financial aspects** would support addressing and comparing sustainability issues. Therefore, the **UN Resource management system** addresses three additional reporting aspects: oversight, operations and regulations to be applied across various resources.

Figure 3-9: United Nations Resource Management System presented by Harikrishnan Tulsidas, UNECE (UNRMS) during the regional workshop south

It was further added that **local stakeholders need to be included in reporting**. This could include information on degraded areas and allow stakeholders to use the statistics to assess whether extraction activities are satisfactory for the goals and needs of the local community. The document “EU principle for sustainable raw materials” could offer a basis for reporting areas within the EU extractive industry; however, no concrete indicators are set in the principles.

While it was generally agreed that mineral data should be openly available and free, it was acknowledged that commercial sensitivity leads to certain data being concealed or anonymised even though such secrecy may not be necessary to maintain business. The need for **clear and accurate data interpretation** was highlighted as important for preventing misunderstandings and for supporting trust.

Reporting results are mostly comparable between EU Member States. However, reporting can demand far too much capacity for SMEs. The reporting requirements for companies (to their shareholders) and governments are different: governments require a wider framework and reporting for addressing issues in the longer term – aspects that are missing in the current reporting standards. This long-term reporting is especially challenging for SMEs.

Presentation on Reporting

The following presentation (available on the [SUMEX website](#) and summarised in Annexes 1-5 below), specifically addressed a practice case and issues related to reporting in the EU:

- “Mineral Resources Management – Slovenian approach” by Duška Rokavec, Geological Survey of Slovenia; [South workshop](#) (22 June 2022)

4 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

The conversations, panel discussions and presentations during the four regional workshops and at the summary workshop in Brussels suggest certain common aspects for promoting sustainable management in the extractives industries. The ability to gain a **social license to operate** (SLO) was seen to be significantly and positively impacted by proper land-use planning, successful environmental impact assessments (EIA) and thorough social impact assessments (SIA), complete implementation of existing health and safety standards, and transparent reporting. Properly addressing each of these four SUMEX Focus areas, and therefore also seriously considering SLO, was perceived as essential to attaining **permitting rights**.

Continuous communication from the beginning of project planning between all actors – citizens in surrounding communities, CSOs, authorities, and industry – was a common theme essential for gaining SLO. It is a **continuous process**, and the dialogue outcomes will certainly change with time. New technologies, development and knowledge will contribute to a transformation and must be considered when drafting and updating legislation and roadmaps supporting society’s and industry’s sustainability goals.

The overall key findings per focus area are summarised into a few key phrases in Figure 4-1.

Figure 4-1: Key findings from peer-learning regional workshops, per SUMEX Focus Area

The presentations from these SUMEX peer-learning workshops and further information on other good-practice cases (see repository and MOOC) are provided on the [SUMEX website](#). The discussions on the topics summarised above will be further supported and accompanied within the framework of the SUMEX project until the end of the project in October 2023. The project supports a LinkedIn channel for its Community of Practice to maintain contact on sustainability in the extractive sector.

5 ANNEXES

5.1 ANNEX 1: WEST REGIONAL WORKSHOP – DIGITALLY HOSTED

West workshop	Details
Target countries	Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Ireland, Luxembourg, Netherlands
Date and duration	23 November 2021; 4 hours
Location	TEAMS, digital platform hosted by Oeko-Institut e.V. (Germany)
Format	Digital
Site visit	None (not possible due to existing COVID-19 Pandemic restrictions and because the event was hosted digitally)
Moderator	Stefanie Degreif (Oeko-Institut e.V.)
Main topics and Key messages	<p>Land-use planning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early engagement of all stakeholders to understand and accept their view and benefits is important from the beginning (but time intensive) • Considering land/ environmental rehabilitation from the project start is important, not too demanding and positively impacts the outcome and legacy of the project <p>Permitting</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rehabilitation should be included in the permitting process
Good practice cases/ presentations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Mineral Development in Ireland, a review of planning and consent” by Sybil Berne (MacCabe Durney Barnes, Ireland) • “Implementation of the Nature directives in EU member states: Guidance for inspection in nature protected areas” by Gisela Holzgraefe (Ministry for Energy Transition, Agriculture, Environment, Nature and Digitalization of the State of Schleswig-Holstein, Germany) and by Lia Mergulhão (ICNF – Instituto da Conservação da Natureza e das Florestas, I.P., Portugal) • “Mining and Postmining in Germany – Examples from the Sauerland Area” by Michael Neumann (independent consultant, Natural Resources Consulting, Germany)
Participant working-group topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The extractive industries and land use planning • The extractive industries and permitting
Participant attendance	33 participants in West workshop
Workshop webpage	https://www.sumexproject.eu/events/sumex-regional-workshop-west/
Snapshot of participant locations	

5.2 ANNEX 2: NORTH REGIONAL WORKSHOP – HELSINKI, FINLAND

North workshop	Details
Target countries	Denmark, Finland, Sweden
Date and duration	20-21 April 2022; 1.5 days (1 day workshop; ½ day site visit)
Location	Helsinki, Finland (Scandic Hotel)
Format	In-person workshop (first day) and site visit (second day)
Site visit	Swerock Malmgård aggregate quarry
Moderator	Pamela Lesser (University of Lapland)
Main topics and Key messages	<p>Socio-economic and environmental impact assessments (SIA and EIA)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social impact assessments are a necessary foundation for projects to acquire their SLO • For social impact assessments (SIA) to be effective: SIA would need to be institutionalised in the whole management life cycle of a mine; trained personnel with experience on how to conduct SIA should be used. • SIA is an important bridging-point for addressing other issues, such as water management <p>Permitting</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Without SLO/ SIA, permitting is very difficult or impossible; SIA should be obligatory. • For successful permitting, industry needs to be present and active in discussions with the community; native language and social understanding helps in discussions. • A facilitator or moderator can be useful to allow a common understanding in discussions.
Good practice cases/ presentations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Industry’s approach to the Water Framework Directive” by Ylva Ågren (Boliden) • “Interactions of community engagement and sustainability” by Ulla Syrjälä (Anglo American) • “Social impact assessment and management meets SLO in small-scale mining” by Rauno Sairinen (University of Eastern Finland)
Expert discussion panellists	<p>Working with the Water Framework Directive</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry/ practice case representative: Ylva Ågren (Boliden) • NGO/CSO representative: Rebecca Burton (Initiative for Responsible Mining Assurance) <p>How do sustainability concepts impact environmental & social impact assessments and permitting?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry/ practice case representative: Ulla Syrjälä (Anglo American) • NGO/ CSO representative: Rebecca Burton (Initiative for Responsible Mining Assurance, IRMA) • Academic representative: Rauno Sairinen (University of Eastern Finland)
Participant working-group topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What impact does the Water Framework Directive have on industry? • What is the social and environmental perspective of community engagement?
Participant attendance	22 participants in North workshop
Workshop webpage	https://www.sumexproject.eu/events/sumex-regional-workshop-north/
Picture from site visit	

5.3 ANNEX 3: EAST REGIONAL WORKSHOP – TALLINN, ESTONIA

East workshop	Details
Target countries	Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia
Date and duration	31 May - 1 June 2022; 1.5 days (1 day workshop; ½ day site visit)
Location	Tallinn, Estonia (Hotel Europa – Hestia group)
Format	In-person workshop (first day) and site visit (second day)
Site visit	Vão quarry
Moderator	Veiko Karu (Tallinn University of Technology)
Main topics and Key messages	<p>Health and Safety</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Need for a ‘Culture of safety’; H&S standards must be implemented. More but concise H&S standards should become law. <p>Permitting</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Natura 2000 areas hypothetically do not exclude mining; they are just very uncommon. Negative legacy is a starting point for any mining project. Community engagement is key.
Good practice cases/ presentations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Health and Safety challenges facing deep underground mine operators – a case study from Polish copper mines” by Krzysztof Fuławka (KGHM CUPRUM R&D) “The unique hybrid business model of combining power storage services and deep granite mining and its environmental footprint” by Peep Siitam (Energiaslv) “Sustainable mining in Natura 2000 zone” by Ivan Ivanov and Gergana Todorova (Dundee Precious Metals)
Expert discussion panellists	<p>Health & safety standards exist, but are they really implemented?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industry/ practice case representative: Krzysztof Fuławka (KGHM CUPRUM R&D) Permitting authority representative: Robert Podolski (independent expert in H&S; former state mining authority) Policy representative: Lilli Tamm (Estonian Environmental Board) <p>How does social license to operate impact permitting processes?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industry/ practice case representative: Peep Siitam (Energiaslv) Industry/ practice case representative: Ivan Ivanov (Dundee Precious Metals) NGO/ CSO representative: Tarmo Treimann (Estonian Environmental Center NGO) Policy representative: Lilli Tamm (Estonian Environmental Board)
Participant working-group topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What impact does the implementation of health & safety standards have on industry? How to tackle legacy issues to reach more social acceptance
Participant attendance	33 participants in East workshop
Workshop webpage	https://www.sumexproject.eu/events/sumex-regional-workshop-east/
Picture from site visit	

5.4 ANNEX 4: SOUTH REGIONAL WORKSHOP – SEVILLE, SPAIN

South workshop	Details
Target countries	Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain
Date and duration	22-23 June 2022; 1.5 days (1 day workshop; ½ day site visit)
Location	Seville, Spain (La Casa de la Ciencia)
Format	In-person workshop (first day) and site visit (second day)
Site visit	Cobre Las Cruces
Moderator	César Luaces Frades, European Aggregates Association (UEPG)
Main topics and Key messages	<p>Reporting</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consider non-financial reporting directive. Environmental data reporting is important to build trust, yet not required; ‘resource blindness’ prevents populations for understanding raw material importance. Industry is “reserved” in full transparency (competitive information). <p>Permitting</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clear communication, being sensitive to exact terms used and long-standing issues, leads to trust between all stakeholders to develop successful projects. Public consultations to include perspectives of people directly in the mining area. pertinent to identify and in detail understand the goals for the Natura 2000 zone to address environmental preservation goals.
Good practice cases/ presentations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “ASSIMAGRA: Permitting procedures and experience in Natura 2000 areas in Portugal” by Nelson Cristo (ASSIMAGRA) “Mineral Data Management: Slovenian Approach” by Duška Rokavec (Geological Survey of Slovenia)
Expert discussion panellists	<p>Permitting and sustainability in Natura 2000 zones</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Practice case representative: Nelson Cristo (ASSIMAGRA) Industry representative: Ana Esther Pérez (Cobre las Cruces) NGO/ CSO representative: Beltrán de Ceballos Vazquez (Plegadis S.L.) <p>Documenting sustainability: Reporting and administrative barriers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy/ practice case representative: Duška Rokavec (Geological Survey of Slovenia) Policy representative: Carmen Marchán, Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (SGM) Policy representative: Harikrishnan Tulsidas, UNECE (UNRMS) NGO/ CSO representative: Željko Pogačnik (Slovenian Surface Mining Association (DTVPO))
Participant working-group topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Permitting and biodiversity barriers Reporting and administrative barriers
Participant attendance	48 participants in South workshop
Workshop webpage	https://www.sumexproject.eu/events/sumex-regional-workshop-south/
Picture from site visit	

5.5 ANNEX 5: SUMMARY WORKSHOP – BRUSSELS, BELGIUM

Summary workshop	Details
Target countries	Entire EU
Date and duration	17 November 2022; ½ day
Location	Brussels, Belgium (Le Plaza Hotel)
Format	In-person workshop
Moderator	Katharina Gugerell (University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences)
Main topics and Key messages	<p>Health & Safety</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Health and safety rules are in place. A culture of real implementation leads to change and decreases accident rates. <p>Closing the loop</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extraction companies need to change their business approach from only primary raw-material production to include recycling and the circular economy. <p>Making sustainability happen</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The EU has many rules to guide industry toward more sustainability in the extractives sector. Strict implementation of these rules is necessary. Nevertheless, adapting the rules is important to guide toward improved sustainability in the future.
Good practice cases/ presentations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Sustainability frameworks and approaches in Europe” by Maria Nyberg (European Commission) and Michael Tost (Montanuniversität Leoben) “Health and Safety challenges facing deep underground mine operators” by Krzysztof Fuławka (KGHM CUPRUM R&D) “Closing the loop in quarry extraction” by Kjartan Eggebø (VELDE)
Expert discussion panellists	<p>What is needed to make sustainability happen?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industry representative: Pablo Libreros, Holcim Group NGO/CSO representative: Michael Reckordt, PowerShift e.V. National Policy representative representative: Riikka Aaltonen (Mineral Policy Finland) EU Policy representative: Maria Nyberg, DG GROW
Participant attendance	82 participants in Brussels workshop
Workshop webpage	<p>https://www.sumexproject.eu/events/making-sustainability-happen-european-extractive-industries-in-the-transition/</p> <p>Agenda: https://assets.swoogo.com/uploads/2193512-6370c75cd53af.pdf</p>
Picture of panelists	

SUMEX PROJECT BACKGROUND

SUMEX is a 36-months project funded by the EC that started on 01.11.2020. The project supports the set-up of a European sustainability framework to improve the permitting procedure along the extractive value chain (prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure, post closure activities), to guarantee timely decisions, a transparent governmental regulatory regime, appealing financial and administrative conditions and sustainable natural environmental and social conditions. The main mission of SUMEX is to assist policymakers and other stakeholders in seizing this opportunity.

To foster more, but sustainable mineral production in the EU, SUMEX (*SU*stainable Management in *EX*tractive industries) will establish a sustainability framework for the extractive industry in Europe. It does so by considering the Sustainable Development Goals, the European Green Deal, as well as EU Social License to Operate considerations and will involve stakeholders from industry, government, academia and civil society backgrounds from all across the EU.

This framework is then applied across the extractive value chain to analyse the mineral, as well as relevant economic, environmental and social policy frameworks of the EU, member states and selected regions along five focus areas – socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, land use planning, health and safety, reporting official statistics and permitting processes/policy integration-to find, or build, where needed, good practices or tools for an open access toolkit, which will be embedded in a broader Community of Practise (CoP) and which forms the basis for capacity building. This CoP will consider relevant stakeholder groups, with a focus on permitting authorities, across the EU, providing a digital platform and using a series of workshops and webinars. In SUMEX, the experience from other projects builds a powerful foundation for addressing the challenge of how best to implement sustainability considerations into the whole raw materials value chain.

Challenge: No common understanding of sustainable management in extractive industries

SUMEX supports the set-up of a European sustainability framework to improve the permitting procedure along the extractive value chain (prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure, post closure activities), to guarantee timely decisions, a transparent governmental regulatory regime, appealing financial and administrative conditions and sustainable natural environmental and social conditions. The main mission of SUMEX is to assist policymakers and other stakeholders in seizing this opportunity.

Objectives of SUMEX

- Strengthen policy coordination and agenda setting along the mineral extraction value chain;
- Propose a uniform EU sustainable management in extractive industries context;
- Cluster with other projects to identify good practices and good practise principles;
- Identify good practises and principles for policy strategies and strategic approaches, coordination/integration and approaches and property rights regimes for different institutional systems;
- Build a toolkit with good practises, with a focus on access to land, permitting and policy coordination and integration;
- Identify stakeholder learning needs and requirements;
- Deploy an open access toolkit for capacity building across EU and with all stakeholders.

More info on <https://www.sumexproject.eu/>

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